

Simultaneous determination of Glipizide and Metformin hydrochloride in pharmaceutical preparation by HPLC

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A new HPLC method for the determination of Glipizide and Metformin hydrochloride in combination has been described. The method is based on reverse phase liquid chromatography using C-18 column and a suitable mobile phase. The detection is done at 225 nm. The flow rate is adjusted at 1.0 ml/min and linearity is established.

Glipizide¹ is 1-cyclohexyl-3-[4-[2-(5-methylpyrazine-2-carboxamido)ethyl]benzenesulfonyl] urea and Metformin hydrochloride² is 1,1-dimethyl biguanide hydrochloride. Metformin hydrochloride is antihyperglycemic but not hypoglycemic³ where as Glipizide is hypoglycemic. Metformin hydrochloride is often given in combination with sulfonyl ureas⁴. Literature survey reveals that some methods^{1,2,5-9} have been reported for the determination of Glipizide and Metformin hydrochloride individually. The present method describes simultaneous determination of two drugs in a single pharmaceutical preparation.

Results and discussion

Precision of the method was proved by observing the low value of RSD (%) in the present analytes (Table 1).

Table 1. Simultaneous assay of Glipizide and Metformin hydrochloride

Label claim : Each uncoated tablet contains; Glipizide : 5.00 mg, Metformin hydrochloride : 500.00 mg

Expt. no.	Glipizide			Metformin hydrochloride		
	Assay %	Error %	RSD* %	Assay %	Error %	RSD* %
1.	100.15	+0.15	0.789	99.92	-0.08	0.615
2.	99.30	+0.70	0.602	100.02	+0.02	0.315
3.	99.90	-0.10	0.512	100.60	+0.60	0.492
4.	100.32	+0.32	0.612	99.30	-0.70	0.519
5.	100.71	+0.71	0.391	100.09	+0.09	0.312

*Each value is average of five determinations.

Accuracy of the method was checked by recovery studies. Placebo was spiked with known quantities of standard drug at the level of 80% to 120% of label claim (Table 2).

Linearity of the method was established by analysis of standard solution containing 1-3 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and 100-300 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Glipizide and Metformin hydrochloride respectively. The calibration curve drawn by plotting the peak area

Table 2. Recovery studies

Sl. no.	Glipizide			Metformin hydrochloride		
	Amount added mg	Amount found mg	Recovery* %	Amount added mg	Amount found mg	Recovery* %
1.	4.00	4.01	100.25	400.00	401.20	100.30
2.	5.00	5.03	100.60	500.00	500.50	100.10
3.	6.00	5.98	99.66	600.00	599.39	99.89

* Each value is average of five determinations.

versus concentration gave correlation coefficient 0.9992 and 0.9996, slope 3798 and 281199 and intercept 50055 and 560055 for Glipizide and Metformin hydrochloride respectively. Specificity of method was established by injecting the placebo of the tablet. No interference of the placebo was observed with the principal peaks, hence the method was found to be specific for these two drugs. Ruggedness of the method was established by carrying out the same experiment on different days, getting the similar analytical data. Robustness of the method was determined by slight change in chromatographic condition, pH (buffer) and temperature. The detection response was found to be satisfactory for both the drugs at the optimum wavelength of 225 nm. The column efficiency determined from the analyte peaks was not less than 1000 theoretical plates. The tailing factor for the analyte peaks was not more than 4.0 and the relative standard deviation for replicate injection was not more than 1.0%. The above method was validated as per U.S.P. guideline¹⁰. The present method is fast, selective precise and reproducible hence it can be used for routine quality control analysis.

Experimental

Water (HPLC grade), methanol (HPLC grade), sodium hydroxide (G.R. grade), ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate (extra pure), pump (Waters 510), UV detector

Fig. 1. A typical chromatogram of Glipizide and Metformin hydrochloride combination : Chromatographic conditions; wave length = 225 nm, flow rate = 1.0 ml/min, run time = 12.0 min, column = C-18 (300 × 3.9 nm), column temp. = 40°, no. of theoretical plates = NLT-1000, tailing factor = 4.0.

(Waters 486), column (Waters, C-18, 300 × 3.9 mm), recorder (Waters 748) and injector (Rheodyne fix loop 20 μ l), were used for the experiment, column temperature maintained at $40 \pm 1^\circ$, wavelength fixed at 225 nm and flow rate maintained at 1.0 ml/min in the experiment.

Phosphate buffer was prepared by dissolving 5.0 g ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate in 500 ml water and adjusted pH 5.0 ± 0.05 with 0.2 M sodium hydroxide.

Suitable mixture of mobile phase was prepared by mixing buffer and methanol (50 : 50) and filtering through a membrane (0.45 μ m porosity). The solution was degassed as usual.

Accurately weighed 5.0 mg of Glipizide (WS) and 500.00 mg of Metformin hydrochloride (WS) were taken in a 100 ml standard volumetric flask. In the above flask 50 ml methanol was added and warmed on water bath. Contents were shaken well and allowed to cool at RT. The above flask solution was diluted with phosphate buffer to full volume (100 ml) and mixed properly. 2 ml of this solution was

transferred to a 50 ml standard volumetric flask and diluted with mobile phase to full volume and mixed properly. A portion of the solution was filtered through a suitable filter of 0.45 μ m porosity and the filtrate was used as standard preparation. Equal volumes (20 μ l) of standard preparation were injected into the chromatograph, the recorded chromatogram and the response of the major peaks were measured. The relative retention time was found to be about 1.0 for Glipizide and 0.43 for Metformin hydrochloride.

20 tablets were weighed and crushed to a fine powder. Powder sample equivalent to 5 mg of Glipizide and 500 mg of Metformin hydrochloride was weighed accurately and transferred in 100 ml standard volumetric flask, which was then proceeded as per direction for standard preparation.

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